

Hearing thought: moving diagrams in Gertrude Stein's *Portraits*

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Abstract. Gertrude Stein's proto-cubist prose (especially the major portion of *Portraits*) is an iconic-diagrammatic experiment of perception of small differences in consciousness. The icon is operationally defined by Charles S. Peirce as a sign whose manipulation reveals, by direct observation of its properties, some information on its object. As soon as an icon can be considered as consisting of interrelated parts, and since these relations are subject to experimental manipulation governed by laws, we are working with diagrams. I explore the idea that Stein developed a method to diagrammatically embodied James' notion of "stream of consciousness". It follows from this argument that Stein's prose cannot be treated as tending towards referential abstraction or focusing exclusively on the materiality of semiotic processes, nor as a shift to pure syntactic or phonological experimentation, since it is concerned with the diagrammatization of flowing thought and its main properties continuity and change.

Keywords. diagrammatic reasoning, protocubist prose, Gertrude Stein, Charles S. Peirce, William James.

"[A] fine new kind of realism"
William James

"Mind is a continuously moving diagram changing in time"
Charles S. Peirce

1. Stein's prose as diagrams (*sensu* Peirce) of the conscious mind:

This is a fragment of Pablo Picasso's proto-cubist portrait —

One whom some were certainly following was one who was completely charming. One whom some were certainly following was one who was charming. One whom some were following was one who was completely charming. One whom some were following was one who was certainly completely charming. Some were certainly following and were certain that the one they were then following was one working and was one bringing out of himself then something. Some were certainly following and were certain that the one they were then following was one bringing out of himself then something that was coming to be a heavy thing, a solid thing and a complete thing.

One whom some were certainly following was one working and certainly was one bringing something out of himself then and was one who had been all his living had been one having something coming out of him. Something had been coming out of him, certainly it had been coming out of him, certainly it was something, certainly it had been coming out of him and it had meaning, a charming meaning, a solid meaning, a struggling meaning, a clear meaning.

(Stein, [1912] 2008, p. 104-105)

Gertrude Stein's work is no longer neglected. In recent decades, a vast number of works about Stein's life and writing have been published in journals, books, book chapters, encyclopedia entries, PhD theses, and monographs. While earlier criticism often oscillated between viewing

Stein's prose as an example of experimental obscurity and linguistic abstractionism, this is no longer the case. Previous studies have been supplanted by meticulous analyses and detailed reconstructions of Stein's original aesthetic strategies.

Stein, the author of experiments in "pure syntax and sound," was always distant from what seemed more aligned with the traditions that influenced major critics, such as analytical psychology, Freudian and Jungian psychology, and cultural anthropology (Dubnik, 1984, p. xiii). Although critics remained unfamiliar with Stein's experiments, structuralism played an important role in transforming the approach to the "Gertrude phenomenon." As Dubnik (1984, p. xiv) notes, "Because Stein's writing does emphasize sound and syntax, insights from linguistics and semiology are useful tools in Stein's criticism." In fact, the problem of approaching Stein still seems to be primarily methodological. Dydo (2003, p. 13) summarizes this difficulty by comparing Stein and Joyce — "Unlike Stein, Joyce can be analyzed and researched with the scholar's tools. In *Modern Music* for April 11, 1934, Gilbert Seldes wrote that Joyce "packs ten meanings into a word," whereas Stein "strips all meanings from words." According to Dydo (2003, p. 17), "Her stripped words cannot be joined by unthinking habit. Their exploration requires thought." In summary, Stein's semantic-pragmatic experiments in emptying the phrasal components of familiar, habitual relations seemed too disconcerting for the academic community. According to Dubnik (1984, p. xiv), "She uses words as if they were new and had no history." For Steiner (1978, p. 107), Stein's emphasis is "[...] on pure sound in language [...], for as soon as a word surface is meant to be perceived as such its aesthetic aspects move to the foreground and the patterning of sounds itself becomes the central point of the work."¹

Our argument here is grounded in a distinct explanatory model — Stein's experiments cannot be categorized as forms of abstraction directly tied to the diminishing or reduction of reference, or even a depletion of semantic properties. The purported de-referentialization of her most radical prose not only fails to equate to the loss of the referent — a vaguely defined condition criticized by commentators — but is the outcome of a diagrammatic iconization (*sensu* Charles S. Peirce) of the flow of thought, according to William James. Continuous shifts in conscious focus are rendered through subtle, cumulative alterations in grammatical and syntactic connections, the buildup of auditory and rhythmic patterns, the parallelism of phonetic structures, and, intriguingly, even graphic arrangements (Dydo, 2003, p. 16). This reflects the iconization of conscious attention as observed through language, which, according to James, exemplifies two key attributes — continuity and change. In other terms, Stein's experiments cannot be described as forms of abstraction, which are typically associated with a loss or decrease in reference. The supposed de-referentialization of Stein's most radical prose not only does not equate to a loss of referent — a status poorly defined by critics — but is instead the result of a diagrammatic iconization of the flow of thought, as described by James.

¹ Perloff is one of the few who questions the more common categorizations of Stein's abstraction. According to Perloff (1979, p. 71), most critics discussing Stein's cubism refer to "non-representational" or "abstract" art, with "flat surfaces," "shifting perspectives," and "intersecting planes." Perloff considers such terms slippery and misleading, as they are not exclusive to Cubism. She prefers to describe the relationship between Cubism and Stein's work through an analogous construction of "[...] tension between reference and compositional game, between a pointing system and a self-ordering system" (Perloff, 1979, p. 34), specifically citing the portrait "Susie Asado."

My approach is grounded in Peirce's mature philosophy of signs.² In 1903, Peirce distinguished between icons and iconic signs, or hypoicons, and briefly introduced a division of the latter into images, diagrams, and metaphors (see Queiroz, 2023; Farias & Queiroz, 2014, 2006; Jappy, 2004). This division is particularly significant for my purposes. One of the key properties of Peirce's notion of a diagram — which has far-reaching implications — is that its application is not limited to “visual images” or “graphical representations.” Peirce defines a diagram as an icon of relations governed by rules and conventions. The concept of “verbal” and “acoustic diagrams” has not been systematically explored; when this topic is addressed, the focus tends to remain on what is conventionally recognized as visual-diagrammatic, such as visual poetry or concrete poetry. In our view, Stein transformed language into a multi-layered iconic system, a consistent diagrammatic representation of consciousness as a process, in line with James's understanding. This iconic system primarily represents relationships, emphasizing the connections between various components of objects and states, their internal arrangements, and their temporal structural organizations. In other words, Stein's protocubist prose — especially in *The Making of Americans* and significant portions of *Portraits* — can be understood as a diagrammatic exploration of the perception of small variations in consciousness. Stein's diagrammatic procedures are distributed across multiple levels, encompassing syntactic, phonetic, and morphological experiments, as well as typographical and graphical explorations. In all these cases, Stein engages in a fundamentally iconic type of operation, grounded in diagrammatic calculations and exercised through relational structures such as sound, and syntax. My focus will be on the *Portraits*. An illustrative example is Stein's "Susie Asado," a portrait of the dancer Antonia Mercé, La Argentina.

Sweet sweet sweet sweet sweet tea.

Susie Asado.

Sweet sweet sweet sweet sweet tea.

Susie Asado.

Susie Asado which is a told tray sure.

A lean on the shoe this means slips slips hers.

When the ancient light grey is clean it is yellow, it is a silver seller.

This is a please this is a please there are the saids to jelly. These are the wets these say the sets to leave a crown to Incy.

Incy is short for incubus.

A pot. A pot is a beginning of a rare bit of trees. Trees tremble, the

old vats are in bobbles, bobbles which shade and shove and render clean, render clean must.

Drink pups.

Drink pups drink pups lease a sash hold, see it shine and a bobolink has pins. It shows a nail.

What is a nail. A nail is unison.

Sweet sweet sweet sweet sweet tea

(Stein, 1990 [1913]. p. 549).

This genre becomes a distinctly new phenomenon in Stein's work. What Stein is portraying is not traditional in subjects and characters. They are portraits of the continued observation of a subject, which both affects and is affected by the act of observation itself.

² I shall follow the practice of citing from the *Collected Papers of Charles Sanders Peirce* (Peirce, 1931– 35, 1958) by volume number and paragraph number, preceded by 'CP'; the *Essential Peirce* (Peirce 1998) by volume number and page number, preceded by 'EP'; *New Elements of Mathematics by Charles S. Peirce* (Eisele ed., 1976) by volume number and page number, preceded by 'NEM'; *Annotated Catalogue of the Papers of Charles S. Peirce*. (Robin ed., 1967) by volume number and page number, preceded by MS and/or I).

Reality for her was not separate from the perception and the perceiver of reality. Her portraits are perfect demonstrations of the identity of object and subject, perceiver, perceived, and perception. Likewise, when she did second portraits, it was at later moments, when both perceiver and perceived had changed. They were truly news. (Dydo, 2003, p. 7)

2. Peirce's threefold signs: icons (with a focus on diagrams), indexes, and symbols explained:

According to Peirce, three primary types of signs underlie meaning processes — icons, indexes, and symbols (CP 2.275). These correspond to relations of similarity (icon), contiguity (index), and law (symbol) between the sign (S) and the object (O) it represents. Icons are signs that stand for their objects through similarity or resemblance, regardless of any spatiotemporal physical correlation with an existing object (CP 2.276). This is because S and O share the same qualities and properties. According to Peirce, “An Icon is a sign which refers to the Object that it denotes merely by virtue of characters of its own, and which it possesses just the same, whether any such Object actually exists or not. It is true that unless there really is such an Object, the Icon does not act as a sign; but this has nothing to do with its character as a sign” (CP 2.247). Any S that represents its O through an intrinsic property of S is an icon of O — “anything that signifies on the ground of its own qualities alone is an icon” (Short, 2007, p. 215). Generally speaking, an iconic sign communicates a habit embodied in an object to the interpretant, constraining the interpreter's behavior due to a shared quality between the sign and the object. In essence, the iconic sign relates itself to its object through a property it possesses, and the sharing of those properties is considered “resemblance.” He defines this as “...an identity of characters; and this is to say that the mind gathers the resembling ideas together in one conception” (CP 1.365). In contrast, if S signifies O due to a “direct physical connection” between them (CP 1.372), then S is designated as an index of O. In this scenario, S is directly influenced by O, and both must exist as occurrences — “An index is a sign which refers to the object that it denotes by virtue of being really affected by that object” (CP 2.248). The notion of spatiotemporal co-variation is the most characteristic property of indexical processes (Atkin, 2005, p. 133). Generally speaking, an indexical sign communicates a habit embodied in an object to the interpretant as a result of a direct physical connection between the sign and the object. Finally, in a symbolic relationship, the interpretant represents the object through the sign via a determinative connection based on law, rule, or convention (CP 2.276). According to Peirce (CP 2.307), a symbol is “a sign which is constituted a sign merely or mainly by the fact that it is used and understood as such, whether the habit is natural or conventional, and without regard to the motives which originally governed its selection.”

We are particularly interested here in a class of iconic signs — the diagram. Diagrams are iconic signs that represent, through the relations between their parts, the analogous relations that constitute the related parts of the objects they represent — “...a Diagram is an Icon of a set of rationally related objects” (NEM 4:316). Diagrams are a special type of icon, especially capable of representing relationships — “A diagram is primarily an icon, and an icon of intelligible relationships” (CP 4.513). They represent, through the relationships between their parts, the relationships that make up the related parts of the objects they represent. A diagram is an arrangement of related parts, and its object can only be an analogous relationship. It is a scheme of its object in terms of relationships between its parts. What makes it suitable for experimentation is the fact that it is constructed through intelligible relationships (CP 4.513). The

diagram not only represents the related correlates but, more definitively, represents the relationships between them as objects of the Icon (Johansen 1993; Stjernfelt 2007). What can be defined as the “physicality of the diagram” thus has the nature and form of a relationship (see Hookway, 2002).

a Diagram is an Icon of a set of rationally related objects. By rationally related, I mean that there is between them, not merely one of those relations which we know by experience, but know not how to comprehend, but one of those relations which anybody who reasons at all must have an inward acquaintance with. This is not a sufficient definition, but just now I will go no further, except that I will say that the Diagram not only represents the related correlates, but also, and much more definitively represents the relations between them, as so many objects of the Icon. (NEM 4:316)

When we think of Peirce’s diagrammatology, existential graphs immediately come to mind — a visual-diagrammatic method for analyzing logical inferences (Queiroz & Stjernfelt, 2011; Queiroz & Moraes, 2013). But according to his semiotic theory of mind, an important part of our thinking is made up of “mental diagrams” (MS 404, EP II:10; cf. Peirce 1997, p. 215–216) — “All our thinking happens with signs of some kind, imagined or perceived. The best thinking, especially in mathematical subjects, is done by experimenting, in the imagination, with diagrams or other schemas.” For Peirce, “reasoning consists in observing an icon” (MS 595, EP II:26), or more precisely, in observing diagrammatic properties of mental signs, which he also describes as “mental diagrams” (MS 404, EP II:10). Regarding the phenomenon of verbal and acoustic diagrams, Peirce himself states that sound sign systems can produce diagrammatic representations of reality — “Such a diagram can be either auditory or visual, the separate parts in one case in time, and in another in space. [...] This method of forming a diagram is called algebra. All speech is nothing more than an algebra, with the repeated signs being words, which have relationships because of the meanings associated with them” (CP 3.418). The temporal distance between words in speech, whose relationships are defined by prepositions and verbs, and the spatial distance between written words, suggest a relationship between objects in a diagrammatic manner. Thus, ordinary language, in such aspects, is similar to algebraic equations (CP 2.279). According to Pharies (1985, p. 48), “sounds can also represent geometrically, as often happens with icons involved in indices, through certain properties of volume, height, and duration. Volume and height are both naturally capable of diagramming the quantity or intensity of any variable. [...] The duration of sounds and the spaces of silence between them are naturally suitable for representing relationships involving time and speed.”

3. Diagramming Jamesian “stream of consciousness”:

“Miss Stein is urging a program of linguistic usage which,
though definitely outrunning James’ demands ...
is nevertheless founded upon a conception of the ‘stream of consciousness’
quite familiar to that of James.”
Dubnik (1984, p. 7)

Two key aspects of the “stream of consciousness” had a significant impact on Stein’s experiments: (i) “thought is always changing,” and (ii) “within each individual’s consciousness, thought is sensibly continuous.” The first principle asserts that “no state once gone can recur and be identical with what it was before” (James, 1890, p. 230). This means that even if we encounter the same external object multiple times, we will never experience the same sensation each time;

our perception of the object will always differ. Stein's experiments, particularly in *The Making of Americans* and *Portraits*, systematically explore various perceptions of the same subject, as if we were observing the subject over time and having consecutive thoughts about them — each distinct from the other. This can be seen as a verbal experiment in reconstructing the thoughts that emerge about the subject during the observation process. The other property is continuity — “The changes from one moment to another in the quality of consciousness are never absolutely abrupt” (James, 1890, p. 237). This property is crucial to the temporal development of an idea or image, as it relies on the repetition and persistence of its components — its duration, retraction, and continual progression.

It is well known that Stein was deeply influenced by the pragmatist philosopher William James, particularly in areas such as human personality, identity, and memory (Levinson, 1941; Hoffman, 1965; Weinstein, 1970; Ruddick, 1982-1983; Dubnik, 1984; Wallace, 2010). She also drew inspiration from artists Paul Cézanne and Pablo Picasso, incorporating techniques like multi-perspective methods, metonymic arrangements, and collage, which resulted in a distinct form of Cubist literature (Hoffman, 1965; Fitz, 1973; Gaddis-Rose, 1976-1977; Steiner, 1978; Perloff, 1979; Lavalle, 2003; Hilder, 2005). Throughout her works, repetition and temporal effects emerge as recurring attributes, stemming from her innovative exploration that combines James's psychological theories with the visual experimentation of Cubism. She transforms time into a new form of perceptual experience, characterized by the “frozen time” effect. This aspect of her writing is both surprising and incendiary, as many authors have noted. Since *Three Lives*, Stein has sought to capture and freeze time. She does so by modeling the characters' perceptions of time and thoughts, as seen in *Melantha*, *The Making of Americans*, and her *Portraits*. Following James's idea that thought is continuous, Stein converts the text into a continuous present moment.

For James (1905, p. 606), the perception of past or future time is always intertwined with our knowledge of the present: “Objects fade out of consciousness slowly. If the present thought is A B C D E F G, the next one will be B C D E F G H, and the one after that C D E F G H I — the lingerings of the past dropping successively away, and the incomings of the future making up the loss.” Stein's interest in time is related to the perception of time as James proposes it. Little by little, the present is left behind and receives new information from the future. This approach to time — the “continuous present,” as Stein used to call it — consists of “a series of similar but not identical statements each perceived as a now. The fact that the sentences are similar but not identical is an imitation of now-perception where everything is in constant flux.” Stein developed many techniques to create the continuous present. On the macrostructural level of the text, there are paragraph reiterations, as if the same paragraph is rewritten in an almost identical form with subtle variations. The sentences are also repeated within the same paragraph and in the following ones, always with small differences. Paragraphs and sentences are composed of a few words that appear again and again. To exemplify, Levin (1999, p. 158) stresses some repetitions in “*Melantha*”, especially of “slowly,” “between them,” and “began” — “The repetition draws the constant new beginning that is every new moment of experience. The words here continue to signify meanings, but their repetition suggests something more than just what the words mean: the temporal, the rhythmic unfolding of conscious experience.”

The repetition produces a new beginning, and a new experience takes place. In the *Portraits*, it is the author's experience watching the portrayed. The writer restarts the sentence or the paragraph again and again because her thoughts are changing, creating a new experience based on the observation of the portrayed person. In “Four Dishonest Ones” (1911), there are successive new beginnings of a sentence in different paragraphs. The repeated use of words like “slowly,”

“between them,” and “began” highlights the perpetual renewal inherent in every moment of experience. This repetition emphasizes the temporal and rhythmic flow of conscious experience. In “Melanctha”, this repetition creates a new experience for the reader. In the *Portraits*, the author’s experience restarts as she observes the portrayed person, and her thoughts change, leading to a new experience based on observation. In “Four Dishonest Ones”, successive new beginnings of sentences appear in different paragraphs, contributing to the exploration of the continuous present.

She is one working. She is one not needing to be changing. She is one working. She is one earning this thing earning not needing to be changing. She is one not needing to be changing. She is one being the one she is being. She is not needing to be changing.
She is earning being one working. She is going on earning being one working. She is working. She is not needing being changing.
She is completely earning being one working. She is helping in this thing, helping completing earning being one working. She is not needing to be changing.
(STEIN, 1974 [1911], p. 216).

According to Perloff (1979, p. 38), since “Melanctha”, “the composition must begin over and over again; the same words [...] and the same sentences are repeated with slight variation, and gradually everything changes.” In the portrait above, this is exactly what we see — repetition and gradual modifications. Another feature linked to the continuous present, evident in the portrait “Four Dishonest Ones”, is the use of verb tense. Augusto de Campos (2006, p. 219) highlights that Stein’s continuous present “favors verbs, especially in gerund form, and repetition.” The consistent use of present participles has the effect of slowing down or altering the conventional syntactical rhythm commonly found in standard English. We can interpret the continuous present as a procedure, and its effect transforms language into a processual phenomenon. According to Weinstein (1970, p. 45), “[...] her stylistic experimentation can be seen as an outgrowth of a writer’s attempt to capture life by language, to capture the process of living by recreating English to make it a language more process-oriented.” Retallack (2008, p. 6) states that Stein’s “continuous present experienced in the pulse of her words was part of her project to register a new time sense peculiar to her era — not to write as though it were still the nineteenth century.” The author asserts (2008, p. 6) that in the conference “Composition as Explanation,” Stein...

[...] radically reconceptualized the nature of what temporal dimension of writing could be, positing the revolutionary idea that one was actually composing the ‘time of the composition’ into ‘the time in the composition’, not by speaking about time but through the arrangement and progression and implied tempi of the words. Grammar could literally score the new time sense.

Rhythm is another aspect related to time in Stein’s work that contributes to intensifying the sense of the present. Rhythm is the materialization of time through the literary text structure, particularly in poetry. Stein explores the effects of rhythm musically in her diverse portraits and other texts. In some of Stein’s portraits, rhythm appears to be more significant than the semantic dimension of the continuous present. For example, Perloff (1979) demonstrates how the rhythm in “Susie Asado”, a 1913 portrait of a flamenco dancer, embodies the beat of the dancer’s shoes, which is distinctive in this type of dance.³ The rhythm is embedded in the structure and is

³ Perloff (1979) provides one of the most precise analyses of Stein’s Cubist experiment in “Susie Asado”, carefully distinguishing various descriptive levels in the process of recreating Picasso’s creative strategies. The rhythmic distribution functions as an isomorphic reconstruction of key elements of Flamenco, capturing its fundamental

perceived in the utterance of the portrait. Scholars frequently highlight the orality of Stein's texts, recognizing the importance of prosody and how rhythm modulates the process of signification and the feeling of time during reading. The repetition and accumulation of similar words, as well as the use of rhymes and insistent monosyllables, result in unexpected rhythmic patterns. According to Bridgman (1970, p. 79), "At its most intense, repetition produced a rhythmic sensation in Gertrude Stein. She referred to its 'louder beating' and to the 'steady sound of repeating.' For a time she reproduced this in her writing."

The repetition of sounds and words in Stein's writing creates a musical quality that intensifies the sense of the present moment, enriching the reader's experience. This repetition heightens the effect of the present and emphasizes the reader's engagement. It also disrupts the traditional narrative structure, resulting in a more fragmented, yet rhythmic, reading experience. The repetitive structures add a musical quality to Stein's writing, enhancing the feeling of the present moment. For Schoenbach (2004, p. 245),

Rhythms and repetitions are far more important in Stein than are pronouncements; her vision of literature is expressed more through a logic of duration than it is through such world-altering Poundian cries as "Make it new!" Stein's most outrageous claims tend not to gain power from the intensity of her conviction nor the purity of her expression, but rather from an intensifying effect – a snowballing logic of repetition and amplification.

The repetitive use of a reduced vocabulary was harshly criticized by the critics of her time. However, according to Wallace (2010, p. 110), "It is not merely the babbling of a brook (or a baby), or sound and fury signifying nothing: it is language signifying how language fits into reality." For Pheulpin (1995, p. 21), the repetition in Stein's work "is the way to penetrate into the internal structure of language and establish a point, a passage within the four-dimensional space of the object presented by the cubist paintings. It is what permits the verbal language to designate the referent, the object, under its multiple aspects and configurations." Also, according to Pheulpin (1995, p. 25), "Gertrude Stein liberates language from its communication function" when using repetition, particularly in the way she does. Weinstein (1970, p. 44) argues that repetition affects the style and content of *The Making of Americans*, revealing the representation of a non-hierarchical reality.

If all people and objects and events are of equal significance, then all the words used to describe the consciousness of this reality are of equal significance. And if all words are of equal significance then the semantic weight of single words matters less than the plastic arrangement of words in terms of the whole flow. [...] Suppose that individual words are no longer used to refer to singular realities but all words are subordinated to the flow itself. Once this device is put into practice the possibilities for word organization are nearly endless. The rigidity of word position in the English language is a product of our insistence that language communicates with optimum clarity semantically.

Language becomes an icon of the present time in flux, mimicking the way we perceive our temporal experience. Although Stein's works frequently deal with mundane themes, careful observation reveals her philosophical view embodied in her experimentation. In Stein's first-phase

building blocks. The semantic dimension humorously and overtly engages with the represented object, incorporating playful references to sexuality — such as "roasted Susie," a direct translation of the Spanish asado.

portraits, there is a noticeable emphasis on the semantic level of events generated by the persistent use of the gerund form. At the structural level, there are repetitions of syntax and sound elements. This coordination of the two elements intensifies the sense of present time and creates the impression that we are witnessing a process. It could be said that the combination of these semantic and structural resources aims to systematically challenge established literary conventions. For Steiner (1978, p. 145), this is another analogy to visual Cubism —

In effect, both Stein and the cubists reversed the treatment of temporality in their arts. Where the subject of a painting normally appears in an arrested moment of time, in cubist art the subject is definitely a temporal object. And whereas literature normally develops its subjects gradually from one sentence to the next, supplying new information as it proceeds, Stein's subjects were to be totally present, fully developed, in each atemporal sentence.

4. Reading Stein diagrammatically:

In *Portraits*, there are no abrupt changes; instead, there are progressive, cumulative, and continuous modifications through slight differences among the sentences. Here is a small fragment of “Orta or One Dancing”, an icon of Isadora Duncan:

Even if she was one being one, even if she was one being one and being that one in being one, even if she was being the one she was being in being that one, even if she was being that one she was being a kind of a one she was come to be of a kind of a one, she was coming to be quite of a kind of a one. (Stein, 1998, p. 285)

Each sentence presents a slightly different perspective of Duncan as observed by Stein. Stein creates a cumulative sequence of subtle differences among the sentences and their constituent parts, or groups of words. New groups of words are juxtaposed, and their positions are slightly altered. Notably, each sentence maintains a strong connection to the previous one and cannot be considered the result of a completely new perception.

*Even if she was one being one,
 even if she was one being one and being that one in being one,
 even if she was being the one she was being in being that one,
 even if she was being that one she was being a kind of a one she was come to be of a kind of a one,
 she was coming to be quite of a kind of a one.*

Figure 1. Arranging the parts of sentences vertically allows us to observe the cumulative effect produced by small changes.

A
 A B a
 a C

The constant use of the present participle has the effect of slowing down or distorting the ordinary syntactical rhythm usually associated with standard English (Dubnik, 1984, p. 11). This seems to be one of the most important properties, related to the temporal development of an idea or image, and based on the repetition and insistence of components — the duration, retraction, and continuous progression of an idea.

She did not use made-up or nonsense words, but she broke the vocabulary down into syllables until they became new words. Selfish became sell fish, two new words with new meanings — not no meanings — and new grammatical possibilities: an adjective turned into two verbs and nouns. And how quick we are to reconstruct sell and fish into a phrase about selling fish! (Dydo, 2003, p. 16)

5. Gertrude Stein's prose — diagrammatic, not abstract: final comments:

Gertrude Stein's experiments rely on the systematic production of cumulative repetition of words and word groups — nothing new at all. Many authors have claimed that she was strongly influenced by William James's investigations into consciousness. Again, this is not new at this point. Based on Peirce's ideas on diagrams, I propose that Stein developed a new diagrammatic method. The *Portraits* can be viewed as a diagram of the stream of thought during the observation of something, or someone. This interpretation challenges the prevailing understanding of Stein's work (as abstraction) and provides a more precise explanation of her experiments as iconic or diagrammatic calculations. For Peirce, an icon can reveal the qualities of its object when consistently manipulated. The icon not only directly presents the qualities of its object but is also the only type of sign that allows for the discovery of something about its object through direct observation (Atã & Queiroz, 2014).

If our approach here is correct, Gertrude Stein developed a type of method to diagrammatically embody the stream of consciousness, revealing important properties of the conscious mind. As a result, it can't be said that Stein's prose is abstract or lacks reference. While many scholars have acknowledged the influence of William James' ideas on consciousness in Stein's work, this review proposes that Stein developed a diagrammatic method, inspired by Peirce's concepts, to capture the 'stream of consciousness' in her writing. Through the consistent manipulation of language, the *Portraits* can be viewed as a diagram of the thought process of observing something. This interpretation challenges the notion that Stein's work is abstract and devoid of reference, instead highlighting its iconic nature and its capacity to reveal qualities of the conscious mind.

According to Dubnik, there are different “kinds of obscurity” that must be considered in Stein's work (1984: xvi), and the most frequently mentioned is related to abstractionism, which critics argue characterizes Stein's prose. Even defenders of Gertrude Stein, such as poet-translator inventors like the Brazilian Augusto de Campos, co-founder of the concrete poetry movement and the principal introducer of Stein's work in Brazil, still echo the idea of "irrationalism and prolixity," with a semantic context that is "often evasive, and even indifferent" (Campos, 1988, introduction) — “In her radical writings, Gertrude practices the most abstract and abstruse prose imaginable” (Campos, 2006, p. 217). In my view, the concept of abstraction cannot be applied here in contrast to strict referentiality (whatever that means, since it's not well-defined). Stein's prose not only *stands for* its referent but also accurately captures its temporal movement, transformation, and modification. But of course, the physical-relational properties are relevant here. Because the language emphasizes physically observed material, it functions as an icon, with the material itself signifying. The object (referent) is a relational, diagrammatic structure that governs the language. The icon signifies through the intrinsic material of which it is composed, and its relationship with its referent depends on this material, its form, and its structure. Its degree of “abstraction,” often associated with referential ambiguity by the community (as if this diminishes the precise effect it produces as an oriented interpretation), does not align with an

increase or decrease in meaning, as critics suggest through a simplistic formula (more abstract = less referential).

Diagrams *stand for* the relations observed in the structure of the represented object through their own structure. The structure of conscious perception is the object of Stein's prose. Stein appears to move closer to painting and further from literary tradition; her direct interlocutors are figures like Cézanne and Picasso. As Juan Gris pointed out, composition determines the subject, and composition is syntax, which itself functions as a diagram. Two processes are clearly described as constituting a dichotomy — operations related to the combination-selection axis and operations related to denotation versus self-reference. Based on this latter dichotomy, Stein produces a highly self-referential text that tends toward a form of abstraction resembling, at least initially, Picasso's cubist experiments through an intersemiotic transposition strategy. This drives her text toward new forms and habits of writing and reading. The misunderstanding lies in assuming that the apparent distance from recognizable, physiognomic objects is necessarily an attribute of abstraction at this level.

My idea here is quite different — Stein employed iconic diagrammatic techniques to explore the limits of language as a modeling system of relations. Diagrams *stand for* relations. The object represented by the diagram is always a relation. In Stein, language operates as open-source diagrammatic system, amplifying the recurring patterns of temporal structures in conscious experience. It can be seen as the physical manifestation of temporal patterns, enhancing the experience of conscious attention (*sensu* James). We saw that the icon is operationally defined as a sign whose manipulation reveals, by direct observation of its relational properties, information on its object. For Peirce, as soon as an icon can be considered as consisting of interrelated parts, and since these relations are subject to experimental manipulation governed by laws, we are working with diagrams. Stein develops an iconic-diagrammatic method to reveal the flow of consciousness about two fundamental properties — continuity and change. The following resources contribute to this semiotic-cognitive effect: (i) symmetrical patterns in syntax, (ii) repetition with phonetic parallelism, (iii) slight rotation of syntactic structures, (iv) rhythmic materiality emphasizing beats, (v) synthetic cuts that abbreviate the reading process by omitting transitions, and (vi) multi-hierarchical inversion, where a secondary aspect takes center stage, displacing or eliminating the expected, more prominent aspect.

Criticism of Gertrude Stein often frames her use of such techniques as a retreat from the “real” or referential, emphasizing instead the physical substrate of language and its paralinguistic dimensions. Yet, from my perspective, this binary collapses — it fails to capture the entanglement of meaning, materiality, and the processes of thought that Stein's work embodies. Stein's work fuses meaning, material, and thought into a single dynamic process. It is accurate to say that the diagrammatic icon is a sign logically dependent on the structure from which it is made — its meaning results from an analogy between structures. But the only way to recognize it as a diagrammatic icon is to manipulate its structure and observe analogies with the represented object — in this case, the conscious attention of a mental state in process. Gertrude Stein provides a precise description of consciousness in her work. Our approach posits that there is no loss of the referent because her writing functions as a diagrammatic icon, an accurate representation of its object.

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